

WP2 - Optimising agroforestry design and management: tools for practitioners and farm advisors

D2.8 TOOLS AND SIMULATION MODELS FOR MICROCLIMATE AND WATER STATUS

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Contents

1	Context.....	2
2	Current State of Tools and Models.....	2
3	DigitAF initiatives.....	3
4	Outside DigitAF initiatives.....	3
5	Future Directions.....	3
6	Conclusion.....	3
7	Acknowledgements.....	3
8	References.....	3

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1 Context

The DigitAF research project (July 2022 - June 2026), funded by the European Commission, aims at a high quality implementation of agroforestry to foster climate change mitigation and adaptation in agriculture and to ensure sustainable management of natural resources. Our goal is to provide the main actor groups with tools answering their needs, in particular digital tools. The three actors' groups that are target by DigitAF are:

- Policy actors: policymakers and administrations concerned with applying agroforestry -related regulations, at regional, national and European levels, who set the scene for the adoption (or not) of agroforestry.
- Practitioners: farmers, landowners and by extension, farm advisers playing an active role in designing and managing AFS and whose choices determine the agronomic, economic, environmental, and social performance at farm-level and beyond.
- Beneficiaries of AF products and services: stakeholders in the value chain, including wholesalers, retailers, organisations trading the carbon sequestration and biodiversity benefits of AFS, and final consumers seeking verification of the benefits of AF in clear and accessible terms.

This report is relevant for the second stakeholders' group and addresses Subtask 2.3.3 of the DigitAF project. This task focuses on the improvement of modelling the microclimate of agroforestry systems and its consequences on the tree and crop water relations.

The presence of trees in agroforestry systems has a substantial effect on the crop's microclimate (Jacobs et al., 2022). Specifically, trees reduce the wind speed, the light availability and the crop temperature, and increase the relative humidity, all of which tend to reduce crop evapotranspiration (ET), which is the sum of soil evaporation and plant transpiration. Because of this, the crop water demand tends to be lower in agroforestry systems. However trees also compete with the crop for water. Trees intercept rainfall and only a fraction of precipitation reaches the ground below canopies. They also uptake large amount of water from the soil to ensure their transpiration, reducing the amount of water available for crops. The crop's water status therefore depends on the balance between the reduced demand and the reduced availability of water. This balance is impacted by a large number of interacting factors, including tree and crop root architecture, soil depth and hydraulic properties, trees canopy structure, tree and crop phenology and climatic conditions. Because of this complexity, process-based models, taking into account many of these factors, are useful tools for improving our understanding and for optimizing agroforestry designs.

In this roadmap we will first briefly review the current status of microclimate and water status modelling in agroforestry systems, thereby identifying the knowledge gaps. Then, we describe the activities within DigitAF to address these knowledge gaps, as well as ongoing initiatives outside the project. Finally, we highlight future directions towards a better representation the crop and tree water status in agroforestry systems.

2 Current State of Tools and Models

The commonly used agroforestry model Hi-sAFe (Dupraz et al. 2019) uses a 3D light competition module, based on ray tracing that calculates light interception based on a simplified tree architecture and spatial arrangement. Crop temperature is calculated based on the energy balance, driven by the intercepted radiation, and is thus taking into account the effect of shading by the trees. Adjustment of the relative humidity due to mixing of crop and tree transpiration, as well as wind reduction by

trees, is currently not included in Hi-sAFe. Other simplifying hypotheses that were made when developing Hi-sAFe could also prove problematic in specific conditions. For example, the simplified canopy geometry (simple ellipsoid) prevents simulating the exact position of tree shade when tree canopies have more complex shapes. Another example is the fact that water stress has a simple multiplicative effect on crop processes, which entails that there is no long-lasting effect of drought: as soon as water stress stops, the simulated plant resumes its growth, while in real life, when soil water goes below the permanent wilting point, there is a lasting effect on plant growth and development.

In DigitAF, we have decided to tackle these last two limitations, because light availability for crops in agroforestry systems is a critical constraint, also in current conditions, and because the occurrence and intensity of drought events is expected to increase substantially with climatic change.

With the increasing availability of LiDAR data, from ground or aerial viewpoints, it is possible to rapidly “scan” entire trees, a process that would take up several days when it was done manually. This opens up the possibility to virtually represent detailed tree architecture and, consequently, to simulate more precisely the interception of light by trees and the shadow patterns they cast on the intercrop. However, there were no user-friendly analysis pipelines to efficiently extract main tree metrics (such as leaf area density) that drive light interception in order to compute shade projections from LiDAR data with reasonable computation time.

For crop water status, knowledge has progressed since the development of soil-crop models, and there are now models that can simulate in details water movement within the different organs of a plant. However, these models (e.g. the SUREAU hydraulic model) do not simulate crop growth, nor the effect of trees on microclimate. Our hypothesis was that it is possible to better represent the potential of agroforestry to adapt agriculture to climate change, especially to increased drought risk, by coupling a soil-crop-tree model with an hydrological model able to predict crop cavitation, thus predicting in which conditions the agroforestry microclimate could prevent crop failure.

3 DigitAF initiatives

3.1 Agroforlight

With Agroforlight (De Swaef et al. 2025), we have developed an intuitive 3D modelling tool designed to simulate light availability for the understory crop in agroforestry systems. Thereto, a user can design an agroforestry scene with trees whose 3D architecture is obtained from detailed quantitative structure models (QSM) from terrestrial LiDAR (Light Detection And Ranging) scans of real trees. The tool consists of an online application, accessible at <https://agroforestry.ilvo.be/agroforlight/> (Figure 1), and the R package *agroforlight* (<https://tdeswaef.github.io/agroforlight/>). By combining architectural detail with high-speed light computation, the model effectively simulates realistic agroforestry systems at high spatio-temporal resolution. This model enables the definition of new hypotheses and provides valuable quantitative insights for precision agriculture practices (e.g. adapt crop management according to position in the agroforestry system) to enhance agroforestry performance.

Figure 1: screenshot of the Agroforlight web interface, accessible at <https://agroforestry.ilvo.be/agroforlight/>

The model simulates both direct and diffuse solar radiation using virtual light sources and a grid of sensor tiles placed on the ground. The QSM-based tree architectures are positioned on the field by the user, either individually, or in rows, and have customizable leaf parameters to reflect species-specific canopy traits. Users can configure field layout, tree species, orientation, and phenology, and run simulations for single moments or entire growing seasons, at a temporal resolution down to 15 minutes. The model outputs are processed using real-world solar radiation data to calculate light intensity at each sensor tile.

The Agroforlight modelling approach accurately replicated observed diurnal and seasonal light patterns from a study on a row of poplar trees in Belgium by Artru (2017). Furthermore, it demonstrated its utility in evaluating the effects of tree size and row orientation in an alley cropping system on the cumulative light availability of hypothetical understory crops, differing in growing season length, such as grass (whole year), winter wheat (15 October until 1 August) and maize (1 May until 15 October). As expected, larger trees reduced light transmission more substantially, with up to 38% reduction for maize under 25 m tall trees. Interestingly, tree row orientation had minimal impact on the total transmitted light available across the whole understory crop. However, orientation strongly influenced the spatial distribution of light within the field. As such, north-south orientations yielded more uniform light patterns, while east-west orientations created pronounced shading gradients. The model also revealed that crop growth period (i.e., for grass, winter wheat or maize) had a minor effect on light availability. In other words, the overlapping period of the crop growing season and the period where leaves are present on the trees does not result in marked differences in light reduction. This suggests that water competition, which is also driven by the presence of leaves on the trees, rather than light, may explain observed yield differences between summer and winter crops. The model's high spatial and temporal resolution also allows for detailed within-day light dynamics and separation of direct and diffuse light components, which are critical for understanding crop photosynthesis.

Agroforlight opens new avenues for applications in agroforestry research and design. E.g., it can serve as a digital twin to augment sparse field measurements, it can guide experimental design, and inform

breeding programs for development of shade-tolerant crop varieties. The model's outputs can be integrated with crop growth models to isolate light effects on productivity.

On a more practical side, the Agroforlight tool can support precision agriculture by identifying zones with distinct light regimes, enabling targeted management practices such as variable fertilization or strip cropping, with adapted varieties or species. The tool also holds potential for forestry applications, such as optimizing canopy management for regeneration or understory planting.

3.2 Modelling cavitation in agroforestry systems

The cavitation process is the apparition of gas bubbles in the plant vessels responsible for sap flow (Mantova et al., 2022; McDowell et al., 2008).. It is caused by through excessive negative pressure flow and leads to embolism, rupture of sapflow, hydraulic failure and thus plant death (Mantova et al., 2022) . Classical soil-crop models such as DSSAT, APSIM, STICS DCENT typically overlook this process because in current and past agricultural contexts, crops have rarely been subject to such extreme events that would lead to cavitation. In addition, advances in the field of ecophysiological modelling of plants and crops are more recent than the period during which the most widely used crop models were developed. Finally, advances in research on hydraulic failure in plants have been made on woody plants, and the transfer and generalisation to herbaceous plants has not yet been made. However, in the context of climate change, with the expected increase in the frequency of extreme events such as drought, it is important to take this process into account to evaluate the resistance of crops to extreme droughts. Current soil-crop models overestimate this resilience because, as we have said, water stress reduces photosynthesis while it lasts, but crops can recover as soon as water availability increases. This is particularly problematic when trying to evaluate the role agroforestry could play in adapting to climate change, since one of the supposed beneficial effect of agroforestry is to buffer extreme events. The solution to this problem could be to couple an agroforestry model with a hydraulic plant ecophysiological model. More specifically, the Hi-sAFe agroforestry model (Dupraz et al. 2019) and the SUREAU hydraulic plant model (Cochard et al. 2021) have been coupled in an effort to better take into account the cavitation process when predicting the resistance of agroforestry systems to climate change.

The challenges we faced during this coupling were numerous. First, both models work at different time steps: one day for Hi-sAFe, one minute for SUREAU. Therefore, we had to find the most adapted way to upscale/downscale variables so that models could exchange data. Second, they do not rely on the same parameters to define a simulation so we had to adapt some parameter values, sometimes by looking for parameters values in the literature, so that both models would simulate the same condition. Finally, they do not represent the same state variables. For example, the loss of conductance (PLC) is represented in SUREAU but not in Hi-sAFe, while the crop biomass is represented in Hi-sAfe but not in Hi-Sureau. Alternatively, the SUREAU model allows to represent the Plant Water Potential and its variation through the day, while the Hi-sAFe model only provides a pre-dawn value of this potential. . Despite these challenges, we now have working code to launch SUREAU every simulated days in Hi-sAFe, using the microclimate and crop height computed by Hi-sAFe.

We first ran some verification simulations of pure agricultural plots (i.e. without trees), on artificially-generated climate scenarios (to perfectly control the duration and intensity of drought, if any). In the absence of extreme events, the coupled model predicts transpiration and water potential values similar to the original Hi-sAFe model. This demonstrates that we managed to calibrate the coupled model correctly. However, comparison of the models in the case of an extreme event (e.g., an intense heat wave, combined with a drought, in April), show that the models diverge, as SUREAU predicts the

death of the plant due to full embolism, whereas the original Hi-sAFe model does not. This highlights the importance of taking into account cavitation when modelling the impact of extreme events.

In the future, simulations of more nuanced scenarios with the coupled model will allow determining the range of conditions in which agroforestry systems buffer the microclimate. This might bring resistance to the crop and/or allow recovery after the extreme event. We expect that this will not always be the case, as trees also compete for water with the crops. Therefore, our objective is to determine in which conditions of soil texture, soil depth, water table level and, of course, climate scenarios, agroforestry could be an efficient adaptation strategy to climate change.

In terms of dissemination of this work, a first presentation of the initial ideas for model coupling has been already presented as a poster to the EURAF conference in Czechia in May 2024. We expect to produce one scientific article on the coupling process itself, highlighting the challenges of coupling agronomical and ecophysiological models (and proposing solutions to overcome these challenges), and one article on the simulation results allowing to better define the range of situations (soil, climate, crop characteristics) in which agroforestry increases resilience.

4 Future Directions

Within the remaining months of DigitAF, we will continue working on the coupled Hi-sAFe - SUREAU model, thereby running scenario simulations in different pedoclimatic contexts for studying the potentially buffering effects of agroforestry on the crop water relations. This is also the scope of the (not DigitAF related) PhD project by Sébastien Fauconnier, under the promotorship of Dr. Mathieu Javaux and Dr. Caroline Vincke (UC Louvain, (2025-2029). Here, a hydraulic model will be developed and validated that enables evaluating how the combination of soil texture and climate impacts the **tree-crop competition for water** in agroforestry systems. This is a crucial aspect in understanding the performance of agroforestry systems.

While **wind** is a significant factor in the energy balance of agroforestry systems, it is still often neglected in integrative models (Dupont et al., 2022). Simplified wind parameterizations are typically used, either by incorporating measurements from meteorological stations (van Oijen et al., 2010, Dupraz et al., 2019) or by reducing wind intensity in ways only valid for monoculture crops (Vezy et al., 2020). To improve predictions of microclimate, future research should target a better understanding of wind dynamics in agroforestry systems.

The coupling of the Hi-sAFe model to the SUREAU model may also serve as a first step towards more connectivity between existing models and tools. As each tool has been developed from specific research questions and objectives, they tend to have complementary aspects. Future work in agroforestry modelling should therefore focus on **modularity**, where tools can be assembled for specific research questions based on existing modules.

5 Conclusion

In the DigitAF project we have tackled two aspects of modelling microclimatic effects in agroforestry systems. Firstly, we developed a user-friendly and fast simulation tool for calculating light availability for the understory crop, using detailed tree architectural data obtained from LiDAR scans. Secondly, we have coupled the agroforestry systems model Hi-sAFe with the hydraulic plant model SUREAU, to enable inclusion of the cavitation process, which potentially has important repercussions on the behaviour of crops in extreme events such as heat waves in combination with drought. This coupling serves as a proof of concept towards more modularity in the use of agroforestry models, where complementarity of different approaches can be exploited.

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